

Job Satisfaction For Teachers Of Special Education Centers In Riyadh

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Abstract

This study aimed to measure the level of job satisfaction among teachers of special education centers in Riyadh in the light of two variables: Teacher gender, and years of experience (less than 5 years, 5-10 years, and more than 10 years). The study sample consisted of (201) teachers who were chosen in a random manner. To achieve the goal of the study, the researchers developed a tool to measure job satisfaction and its final form consisted of (32) items, where the results of the study showed that the level of job satisfaction with the study sample was average. The results of the study also indicated the presence of differences in job satisfaction according to the variable of the teacher's gender, in favor of males, and to the presence of differences in the level of job satisfaction according to the variable of years of experience, for the benefit of teachers whose experience exceeds (10 years and more).

Introduction

The success of the educational process depends on the teacher's success in performing the role assigned to them inside the classroom. The teacher remains the main factor in this field, as they organize the experience and execute it in the direction of achieving the desired goals of the educational process. In fact, the teacher's role is no longer limited to indoctrination of the learner with various types of knowledge, but has also become organized and facilitated to give the learner the skills and experiences that build an integrated personality (AlAjiz, 2007).

Previous Studies

Arab study (2011) aimed to identify the differences in the level of professional satisfaction among teachers of special education in Al Majmaah Governorate, Saudi Arabia. The sample of the study consisted of (42) male and female teachers chosen in a simple random method. The results of the study showed that the highest levels of satisfaction were on the economic aspect, followed by the relationship with the management, then the relationship with the students, followed by the social level, then the relationship with colleagues, then self-satisfaction, followed by satisfaction with the tools and equipment. The relationship with the parents of students came in the last rank, and all were positive except teacher satisfaction toward tools and equipment.

The Voris study (Voris, 2011) aimed to reveal the relationship between job satisfaction and self-efficacy among special education teachers in Kentucky, USA. The sample of the study consisted of (222) male and female teachers, including (122 male and 100 female teachers), and the results showed a statistically significant correlation between job satisfaction and self-efficacy. Also, it was found that the degree of satisfaction among teachers of special education is medium, and no statistically significant differences in effectiveness and job satisfaction attributed to gender and experience variable.

The Study's Importance:

The significance of this study due to the variables that have been addressed and the extent of its impact on special education teacher's lives, specifically the bachelor's degree holder of them. As they constitute an important segment of teachers and they play an important role in building students with special needs personalities.

Study's Approach:

To achieve the purpose of the study, a descriptive analytical approach will be used to suit its nature to understand the level of job satisfaction according to gender variables as well as years of experience.

Study population and sample:

The study population consists of all special education teachers within the special education centers and schools in the governorate of Riyadh for the academic year (2019-2020). Where in which special education teachers' overall number is (500) male and female teachers. A random sample consisting of (300) was chosen, of whom (201) answered the study tool that was distributed electronically.

Validity and reliability of the tool:

The study tool was developed in its preliminary form, then (10) experts within the special education field were consulted to give their feedback on the survey's items in terms of their belonging to study's domains and its language and clarity. Based on experts' feedback and recommendations the tool was modified. The modifications were made when two experts agreed to change an item or exclude it from the tool. Moreover, a pilot sampling for study's tool conducted on (30) special education teachers who reflect the original study's sample to examine the instrument validity and reliability. The Correlation coefficients were calculated between the score of each scale's domain and the other domains in the overall scale. The Correlation coefficients were significant, which ranged between (0,58-0,80). Also, Stability coefficients were extracted by calculating the stability coefficient using the Alpha Cronbach equation. Stability coefficients and internal consistency coefficients for the scale ranged from (0,92) and this is statistically acceptable. Indeed, this value was considered appropriate for the purposes of the study, thus, the scale has acceptable sincerity and reliability, which justifies its use for the purposes of this study. Then, this tool was prepared in an electronic version and distributed also electronically to the study population.

To correct the responses of the study instrument, the researchers gave the following scores to the assessment categories:

Score (5) for the first level (applies with a very high degree), Score (4) for the second level (applies with a high degree), Score (3) for the third level (applies with a moderate degree), Score (2) for the fourth level (applies with a low degree), Score (1) for the fifth level (applies with very low degree). Accordingly, the highest score that the participant can obtain is: $(32 \times 5 = 160)$ degrees, and the lowest degree they can get is: $(32 \times 1 = 32)$ degrees. Moreover, the researchers adopted defined standard to determine the degree of teacher satisfaction where the score considered: (high) if the average answer (more than 117,33), (middling) if the average answer (74,67-117,33), and (low) if the average answer is less than (74,67).

Study results:

1. The first question: What is the level of job satisfaction for special education teachers in Riyadh Province from their point of view?

To answer this question, the researchers extracted the arithmetic averages and the standard deviation of the level of job satisfaction among special education teachers in Riyadh province based on their response to study's scale it is clear that the level of job satisfaction for special education teachers in Riyadh province based on their answer is average, (99.18) and with a standard deviation (23.10).

This outcome could be perceived considering different challenges that might confront special education teachers due to their work with individuals with disabilities. Some of which are related to individuals with disabilities themselves, and their parents, while other difficulties are related to the work nature. Working with students with disabilities mostly is very demanding and overwhelming. As known, complications individuals with disabilities having vary in its severity and complexity. Thus, this would impact on their skills and capabilities to achieve the expected level of progression within a specified time. In fact, students with disabilities require intensive efforts and longer time to accomplish their goals—this usually falls on special education teachers with limited parental involvement and high expectations of their children achievement. Modest result that special education teacher accomplish with the student has an impact on their level of satisfaction since job satisfaction has a great link to achievement.

Accordingly, current study results show an average level of teacher job satisfaction which is consistent with result of (Voris, 2011; Al-Muqabli, 2011; Al-Afaraj, 2012). This finding differs from the study result of (Abu Jarad, 2015). ; Ahmet & Fahriye, 2015; Shi & Howe, 2016) that showed high level of job satisfaction. Current results also differ from Abu Zaid study (2017), which revealed low job satisfaction. Indeed, researchers believe that the continuous exposure to the previous discussed challenges may possibly affect special education teachers emotionally and physically in form of mental exhaustion. Consequently, these negative effects of burnout may spill over into many aspects—including teacher's productivity and his/her job satisfaction. Therefore, more attention on understanding job satisfaction and factors related to it need to be given.

The second question of the study examines job satisfaction in relation to gender differences. The question was: Are there statistically significant differences in the level of job satisfaction among special education teachers in Riyadh governorate due to the gender of the teacher (male-female)? Results show that there are statistically

significant differences in job satisfaction levels attributable to gender variable in favor of males. To answer this question, a test (T) was used to examine the differences between the mean scores of the study sample. Arithmetic averages, standard deviations and test results (T)

This result could be read within the cultural context of Saudi society where male educators are accountable financially to their families more than females. Researchers suppose that this might qualify males sometimes to bear the pressures of work and be patient of it, while female teachers might be able to express their dissatisfaction of work stressors due to less financial obligation toward her family.

The results of this study are consistent with the results of the Shtayat study (2018), while it differs from the results of (Abu Jarad, 2015; Ahmet & Fahriye, 2015; Shi & Howe, 2016) studies which indicated that there were no difference in job satisfaction in relation to teachers gender. In addition, current results differ from the result of (Al-Muqabli, 2011 & Arab, 2011) studies where the differences in job satisfaction were in favor of females.

Results related to the third question: Are there statistically significant differences in the level of job satisfaction among special education teachers in Riyadh governorate attributed to years of experience (less than five years, between five and ten years, and more than 10 years)? To answer the question, the researchers calculated the sum of total answers for each member of the study sample to find the arithmetic mean and the standard deviation for these answers. Then, variance analysis applied to find averages differences related to teachers' years of experience.

The sample responses according to their experiences. the number of teachers in the first group is 88, their arithmetic mean is 95.90 out of 160, and the standard deviation is 21.559. The second category was 83, with a mean of 98.80 and a standard deviation of 24.623. The third category has 30 teachers with a mean of 109.93 and a standard deviation of 20.470.

In order to determine whether there were any statistically significant differences in the level of job satisfaction of the teacher within the special education centers in Riyadh according to years of experience (less than 5 years, 5 to 10, 10 and more), Single-phase analysis of variance test was performed to examine the differences between the arithmetic averages on the job satisfaction scale

Thus, it is evident from the previous table that the calculated value of (P) is 4.286, while the statistical significance reached 0.015, meaning it is less than 0.05, this indicates that there are statistically significant differences due to the number of years of experience. In order to identify the reason behind these differences researchers applied Scheffe' Test

the existence of statistically significant differences in the average between two groups of teachers in terms of their job satisfaction related to years of experience. The first group of teachers who have less than five years of experience, and the third group of teachers who have more than ten years of experience. The difference between the two averages was -14.03561 * and the statistical significance for this difference is 0.015, that is, it is less than 0.05, and it was in favor of the third category (10 years and more). Additionally, the result illustrated within the table showed that differences between other averages were not statistically significant. Therefore, researchers believe that the difference in job satisfaction average between the two groups might be due to the fact that highly-experienced teachers have met their needs by obtaining incentives and participating in administrative work, and that they are more satisfied with their social relationships comparing with teachers who are less than five years of experience.

These results can also be explained by considering that the more years they spend working in the teaching profession, the more skills and experiences they acquire and develop to build good social bonds not only with the supervisory body, managers and, peers; but also with parents of children with special needs. Teachers with long experience may also have good coping techniques dealing with work stress. Moreover, prolonged employment in the teaching profession may lead to more job stability and less intent to quit.

In contrast, teachers with less than 5 years of experience may be in a vulnerable position due to their limited experience in dealing with work pressures, students with special needs, and limited social connection with their peers, educational supervisors, and managers. All these factors, along with their aspiration to achieve a promising future, may negatively affect their level of job satisfaction.

Indeed, The study results are consistent with the results of (Interview, 2011; Al-Tubaiti and Al-Anzi, 2014) studies and differ from the results identified by (Arab, 2011; Abu Jarad, 2015; Ahmet & Fahriye, 2015; Shi & Howe, 2016; Abu Zaid study, 2017 Shanatat, 2018) which indicated that there was no difference in satisfaction according to years of experience.

Recommendations

1. Enhancing and developing the leadership skills of special education schools principals and enabling them to apply modern leadership style.
2. Improving and diversifying educational supervision methods and using modern supervision methods
3. Developing and improving the system of incentives and promotions in special education centers, taking into account the competencies of teachers and their professional achievements
4. Promoting teachers' professional development and keeping them informed with new teaching methods.
5. Conducting more studies on job satisfaction for special education teachers focusing on other variables not covered in this study.

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